

Annual Regional Sustainable Development Conference 2025

“BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT, TRANSFORMATION TO GREEN ECONOMICS, AND REGIONAL SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT”

Binh Dinh, Vietnam

3-4 July, 2025

Acceptance letter

Dear **Professor Vătămă Dan,**

We are very pleased to inform you that your manuscript entitled **“THE EUROPEAN UNION ENGAGEMENT ON CLIMATE ACTIONS WITH COUNTRIES FROM ASIA-PACIFIC REGION. Case Study: Establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership with Viet Nam”** has been accepted for presentation at the Annual Regional Sustainable Development Conference 2025.

Venue: Quy Nhon City, Binh Dinh, Vietnam.

Date: 3-4 July, 2025

If you have any further questions, please do not hesitate to email us at aissc.dn@gmail.com. Again, thank you for submitting your article.

We are looking forward to your participation.

Yours sincerely,

For and on behalf of the conference board

HOANG Hong Hiep